

ACCRETION/EJECTION DIAGNOSTIC IN YOUNG STELLAR OBJECTS: A MULTI-BAND AND INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACH

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H α AND FORBIDDEN EMISSION LINES ACCRETION/OUTFLOW

σ Ori
(Rigliaco et al. 2009)

(Reipurth et al. 1996)

- ◆ proxy accretion/outflow
- ◆ variability
- ◆ velocity of the infalling/outflowing plasma

(Bonito et al. 2020)

SKY SUBTRACTION AND H α + [NII]

06392550+0931394 (CSIMon-006491)

OH α NA-method

MASS ACCRETION RATE AND FWZI

$$\log(\dot{M}_{\text{bestfit}}) = -14.64(\pm 0.47) + 0.39(\pm 0.03) \times \text{FWZI}(H\alpha)$$

$\text{OH}\alpha\text{NA}$ -method

NGC 2264

Gaia-ESO Survey

(See also the cases of
NGC 6611, Bonito et al. 2013 and
NGC 6530, Prisinzano et al. 2019)

(Bonito et al. 2020)

X-ray vs. optical band

Bonito et al. (2010 a)

Bonito et al. (2008)

Bonito et al. (2011)

Red-shift in accreting stars

Observations
(Argiroffi, Drake,
Bonito et al. 2017)

Redshift: 35 km/s
First detection
Infalling material
Geometry

LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS: Jets

(Andrea Ciardi)

Density

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REPORT

Laboratory formation of a scaled protostellar jet by coaligned poloidal magnetic field

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Parameters :

$B = 10 \text{ mG}$, Mass ejection rate = $10^{-7} M_{\odot}/\text{yr}$

Ramses code:
Teyssier et al. (2002)

LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS: Accretion

SCIENCE ADVANCES | RESEARCH ARTICLE

ASTROPHYSICS

Laboratory unraveling of matter accretion in young stars

Guilhem Revet,^{1,2} Sophia N. Chen,^{1,2} Rosaria Bonito,^{3,4} Benjamin Khier,⁵ Evgeny Filippov,^{6,7} Costanza Argiroffi,⁴ Drew P. Higginson,^{2,8} Salvatore Orlando,³ Jérôme Béard,⁹ Marius Blecher,¹⁰ Marco Borghesi,¹¹ Konstantin Burdonov,¹ Dimitri Khaghani,¹² Kealan Naughton,¹¹ Henri Pépin,¹³ Oliver Portugall,⁹ Raphael Riquier,^{2,14} Rafael Rodriguez,¹⁵ Sergei N. Ryazantsev,⁷ Igor Yu. Skobelev,^{6,7} Alexander Soloviev,¹ Oswald Willi,¹⁰ Sergey Pikuz,^{6,7} Andrea Ciardi,⁵ Julien Fuchs^{1,2*}

Accretion dynamics in the formation of young stars is still a matter of debate because of limitations in observations and modeling. Through scaled laboratory experiments of collimated plasma accretion onto a solid in the presence of a magnetic field, we open a first window on this phenomenon by tracking, with spatial and temporal resolution, the dynamics of the system and simultaneously measuring multiband emissions. We observe in these experiments that matter, upon impact, is ejected laterally from the solid surface and then refocused by the magnetic field toward the incoming stream. This ejected matter forms a plasma shell that envelops the shocked core, reducing escaped x-ray emission. This finding demonstrates one possible structure reconciling current discrepancies between mass accretion rates derived from x-ray and optical observations, respectively.

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LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS

Asymmetric accretion structure upon slanted matter impact in young stars (Burdonov et al. 2020)

shock

LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS

Asymmetric accretion structure upon slanted matter impact in young stars (Burdonov et al. 2020)

Laboratory experiments of EXOrs (Burdonov et al. 2021)

LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS

Laboratory disruption of scaled astrophysical outflows by a misaligned magnetic field

G. Revet, B. Khair, E. Filippov, C. Argiroffi, J. Béard, R. Bonito, M. Cerchez, S. N. Chen, T. Gangolf, D. P. Higginson, A. Mignone, B. Olmi, M. Ouillé, S. N. Ryazantsev, I. Yu. Skobelev, M. I. Safronova, M. Starodubtsev, T. Vinci, O. Willi, S. Pikuz, S. Orlando, A. Ciardi

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NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS:

(Orlando et al. 2013;
Bonito et al. 2014)

Magneto-hydrodynamic
MHD
(PLUTO code, Mignone et al. 2007)

Radiative losses
Thermal conduction
Gravity
Stellar atmosphere

Radial profile:
 $n = 5 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3} - 5 \times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-3}$
(as suggested by
Romanova et al. 2004)
(Bonito et al. in prep.)
Spectral synthesis of
the
UV and X-ray
emission

Exploring the effects of:

- local absorption
- geometry
- Doppler shift

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

OVII

(Bonito et al. 2014)

Ne IX

ACCRETION SHOCKS: UV/X

Figure 1

Figure 3

Figure 2

(Bonito et al. in prep.)
 (Argiroffi, Drake, Bonito et al. 2017)

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

OVII

Ne IX

YSO-ALESA
method

(Bonito et al. in prep.)

OVII

Ne IX

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

Ne IX (Bonito et al. in prep.)

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

Ne IX (Bonito et al. in prep.)

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

Ne IX (Bonito et al. in prep.)

ATHENA X-RAY OBSERVATORY

- Improve the statistics of accreting young stars
- Different properties (age, mass, geometry, ...)

Multi-band characterization of accretion/ejection process

Transients and variable stars:

Non-degenerate eruptive variables: accretion burst (EXOrs)

Chair: Sara Bonito

(Bonito & Hartigan et al. 2018;
Bonito & Venuti et al. 2021)

Stars, Milky Way & Local Volume:

Variable Stars; Star Clusters:

- Study of accretion and outflow processes in young stars
- Completing the census of young star clusters and probing their formation history, evolution and dispersal by investigating their low-mass populations

Thursday

Cool Star Science with the Rubin Observatory - Discussion led by Bonito

- Transients and Variable Stars with Rubin LSST data
- International collaborations in Rubin LSST
- Observing strategy & Rubin Science Platform
- Justice, Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion in Rubin

Multi-ba

Transien

Non-de

Chair: S

rocess

(EXOrs)

CET	UTC	EST	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday
			02 March 2021	03 March 2021	04 March 2021
			Stellar systems, clusters, and associations	The Sun and the Heliosphere	Post main sequence cool stars
18:00-19:00	17:00-18:00	12:00-13:00	Plenary session	Plenary session	Plenary session
19:00-19:15	18:00-18:15	13:00-13:15	Plenary session (Haikus)	Plenary session (Haikus)	Plenary session (Haikus)
19:15-19:45	18:15-18:45	13:15-13:45	Plenary session	Plenary session	Plenary session
19:45-20:00	18:45-19:00	13:45-14:00	Coffee break + Posters	Coffee break + Posters	Coffee break + Posters
			Young stars	The Sun - Very low mass stars	Globular clusters and Main Sequence stars
20:00-21:00	19:00-20:00	14:00-15:00	Plenary session	Plenary session	Plenary session
21:00-21:15	20:00-20:15	15:00-15:15	Plenary session (Haikus)	Plenary session (Haikus)	Plenary session (Haikus)
21:15-22:00	20:15-21:00	15:15-16:00	Plenary session	Plenary session	Plenary session
22:00-23:00	21:00-22:00	16:00-17:00	Topical interest room 1, 2, 3 / social meeting	Topical interest room 4, 5, 6 / poster session	Topical interest room 7, 8, 9

Cadence choice

Higher

cadence observations are needed in order to clearly characterize the physical mechanisms (Stauffer et al. 2014). As an example, Venuti et al. 2014 explored the mid-term variability

obtaining ≈ 17 points distributed over the 2-week long survey to probe variability. Stauffer et al. 2014 found a burst frequency of 0.2 peak per day and typical total duration of isolated accretion burst of 1 d. Therefore we expect to be able to observe 1 peak in about 5 days,

John Stauffer

(Bonito & Hartigan et al. 2018;
Bonito et al. in prep. b)

Conclusions

- Multi-band analysis (optical, UV, X-rays)
- Future: Athena X-ray Observatory, Vera C. Rubin LSST (multi-band characterization)

The new approach

Combining:

- ✓ laser experiment
- ✓ numerical models of astrophysical jets
- ✓ observations of stellar jets